

SHORT NOTES

SODIUM CHLORITE AS A VOLUMETRIC REAGENT

BY RAM CHAND PAUL AND APAR SINGH

Sodium chlorite is commercially available as a white finely divided crystalline material and is only slightly hygroscopic. Freshly prepared solutions are clear and colorless, but more concentrated solutions gradually turn yellow and then yellowish green if allowed to stand exposed to light. But solution of sodium chlorite, when kept in dark bottles (black painted), is quite stable for several months.

Sodium chlorite liberates iodine from potassium iodide solution in the presence of acid, and this reaction may be used for the determination of the strength of the chlorite solution. According to Bray (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 55, 576) for the determination of chlorite by thiosulphate titration, five minutes may be allowed for the reaction to proceed to completion before titrating in presence of acetic acid. Many other authors have proposed alternate procedures involving the use of phosphoric and sulphuric acids. Brown (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 7, 494) has investigated all the procedures and supports the use of sulphuric acid. He has also stressed the necessity of adding potassium iodide solution to the chlorite first, as the addition of the acid first will produce chlorine dioxide and may give rise to low results.

This reagent has been successfully used as an oxidising agent for the determination of sulphurous acid, bisulphites and sulphites by Jackson and Parson (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1937, 9, 250). The oxidation is smooth and easily controlled and is believed to proceed as

In the present investigation, use has been made of the oxidising power of ICl to preoxidise various substances and of sodium chlorite to reoxidise the liberated iodine to I^+ in the presence of an excess of hydrochloric acid and potassium bromide to give the complex stable ion $(\text{IBr}_2)^-$ which is not appreciably dissociated. Lang (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1935, 106, 13) carried out a detailed study of the procedures involved and his modification of Andrews' titration has been used here with sodium chlorite as the oxidising agent. By this process potassium iodide, arsenious oxide, hydrazine sulphate, ferrous sulphate, potassium sulphocyanide, thalious chloride, mercurous chloride, stannous chloride, potassium ferrocyanide and hydroquinone were preoxidised with iodine monochloride and the liberated iodine was oxidised with standard sodium chlorite to the complex $(\text{IBr}_2)^-$ in the presence of a saturated solution of potassium bromide.

Sodium chlorite has also been used for the estimation of phenol and amines by using it as a bromometric reagent. Quantitative bromination method for the determination of phenol was described by Koppeschaar (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1875, 15, 2531). Paul and Singh (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 328, 605; 1955, 32, 599, 736) have used chloramine-B and potassium metaperiodate as bromometric reagents for the estimation of various inorganic ions and organic compounds. Bromine required in the present work for bromination was obtained according to the equation,

and by this method 2:4-dinitrophenol, *m*-nitrophenol, phenol, *p*-chlorophenol, anthranilic acid, *m*-nitroaniline, *p*-chloroaniline, *o*-nitroaniline and thiourea have been quantitatively estimated, following the method outlined by Paul and Singh (*loc. cit.*).

In the determination of 8-hydroxyquinoline, the modification of Fleck, Green and Ward (*Analyst*, 1934, 59, 325) has been followed. Thus, many metals may be determined indirectly by precipitating their metallic oximates with 8-hydroxyquinoline from their salt solutions and the organic component of the oximate may then be determined bromometrically with sodium chlorite as usual.

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ON THE APPLICATION OF VORTMANN-FORBES REACTION TO ANTIMONY OXIDE AND THIOSULPHATE

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The reaction between antimony trioxide in alkali-lye and sodium thiosulphate was studied by Meyer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1498) and suggested as a clock reaction. Vortmann (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2307) found the reaction between antimony trichloride and sodium thiosulphate to correspond with that of arsenious acid. Venkateswarlu (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 291) confirmed the existence of a minimum period of induction in the arsenious acid-sodium thiosulphate reaction in acid medium. The present work was undertaken to ascertain the existence of a similar minimum period of induction in the antimony oxide and thiosulphate reaction in presence of acids.

Procedure.—The apparatus was thoroughly cleaned with chromic acid and perfectly dried. The chemicals used were of B.D.H. sample. Sb_2O_3 was exactly weighed out for normal solution and double the amount of tartaric acid was added, followed by water. The mixture was slightly warmed to obtain a clear solution,